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Germplasm improvement

Genetics

Analysis of seed, cytoplasmic, and maternal genetic effects on rice quality traits

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We analyzed the genetic effects of seeds, cytoplasm, and the maternal plant on milling quality traits of rice by using the genetic model for quantitative traits of endosperm in cereal crops. Nine cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines and five restorer lines of indica rice were used in an incomplete diallel cross (9×5) during the 1994 early season. Seeds of parents and F_1 s were sown on 28 Mar in the field at ZAU and single plants were transplanted on 29 Apr at 20×20 -cm spacing, with 24 plants per plot and three replications. Seed samples of parents or F_1 s were taken at maturity from eight plants in the middle of the plot. Quantitative traits were measured for each sample of parents, F_1 s, and F_2 s, using three replications.

Milling quality traits were controlled by seed, cytoplasmic, and maternal genetic effects (Table 1). Maternal effects were more important than seed effects for brown rice recovery (BRR) and milled rice recovery (MRR). Seed effects mainly controlled brown rice weight (BRW), milled rice weight (MRW), and head rice recovery from milled rice (HRR). Cytoplasmic effects accounted for 4.1–37.3% of the total genetic variation and were significant for all milling quality traits. Significant additive covariance and dominance covariance were not detected, indicating no relationship existed between seed and maternal genetic effects for these milling quality traits.

Seed and cytoplasmic heritabilities were important for BRW, MRW, and HRR, but seed and maternal heritabilities mainly affected MRR. Additive correlation was important between BRW and MRW, BRW and MRR, BRW and HRR, and MRW and MRR (Table 2). ■

Table 1. Estimated genetic variances, covariances, and heritabilities of milling quality traits in indica rice.

Parameter ^a	Brown rice weight	Milled rice weight	Brown rice recovery	Milled rice recovery	Head rice recovery from milled rice
V_A	8.285** ^b	4.184**	0.000	19.181**	160.667**
V_D	0.499**	0.335**	2.236**	6.494**	45.132**
V_C	2.340**	2.128**	2.598**	2.373**	169.232**
V_{Am}	5.308**	2.863**	0.000	19.630**	0.000
V_{Dm}	1.257**	1.270**	3.648**	9.913**	79.054**
$C_{A,Am}$	-4.264	-1.547	0.000	-0.402	0.000
$C_{D,Dm}$	-0.300	-0.233	-1.329	-3.863	-19.051
V_e	0.183**	0.146**	1.011**	1.334**	5.033**
h_o^2	0.460**	0.358**	0.000	0.373*	0.382**
h_m^2	0.119	0.179	0.000	0.382*	0.000
h_c^2	0.268*	0.289*	0.380	0.047	0.402**

^a V_A = additive variance, V_D = seed dominance variance, V_C = cytoplasmic variance, V_{Am} = maternal additive variance, V_{Dm} = maternal dominance, $C_{A,Am}$ = covariance between seed and maternal additive effects, $C_{D,Dm}$ = covariance between seed and maternal dominance effects, V_e = variance of residual effects, h_o^2 = seed heritability, h_m^2 = maternal heritability, and h_c^2 = cytoplasmic heritability. ^b*, ** = significant at 5 and 1% level, respectively.

Table 2. Correlation components between milling quality traits in indica rice.

Traits	Seed additive correlation	Seed dominance correlation	Cytoplasmic correlation	Maternal additive correlation	Maternal dominance correlation	Residual correlation
BRW and MRW	0.720** ^a	0.540**	0.477**	0.509**	0.426**	0.100
BRW and BRR	0.000	-0.093*	0.378**	0.000	0.032	0.159*
BRW and MRR	0.596**	-0.334**	0.135**	0.311**	-0.001	-0.118
BRW and HRR	0.486**	-0.126**	-0.253**	0.000	0.041	0.123*
MRW and BRR	0.000	-0.251**	0.571**	0.000	0.075	-0.136
MRW and MRR	0.364**	0.009	0.453**	0.145**	0.119**	0.344**
MRW and HRR	0.174**	0.175**	-0.349**	0.000	0.066	0.123*
BRR and MRR	0.000	0.258**	0.496**	0.000	0.264**	0.269**
BRR and HRR	0.000	-0.172**	-0.393**	0.000	-0.157**	-0.059
MRR and HRR	0.314**	0.208**	-0.310**	0.000	0.182**	-0.008

^a*, ** = significant at 5 and 1% level, respectively.

Tall and dwarf near-isogenic lines of indica rice characterized

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The effects of the semidwarf gene *sd1* on agronomic traits in indica rice were studied using seven tall and dwarf near isogenic lines (NILs) bred by semidwarf^{8/} tall varieties (B_7F_2) (see figure).

Tall and dwarf NILs Ainanai 1^{8/} Liantangzao (T1 and D1), Erjiqing^{8/} Liantangzao (T2 and D2), Fulianai^{8/} Liantangzao (T3 and D3), Erjiufeng^{8/} Liantangzao (T4 and D4), Guangluai 4^{8/} Liantangzao (T5 and D5), Erjiufeng^{8/} Lucaihao (T6 and D6), and Guangluai 4^{8/}

Lucaihao (T7 and D7) and their parents were transplanted according to their height in different plots at 15×15 -cm spacing in 1993.

Agronomic traits (days to heading, flag leaf length and width, plant height, panicle length, internode length, effective panicles per plant, spikelets per panicle, 1,000-grain weight, yield per plant, biomass, and harvest index) were measured for 20 plants in the middle of the plot.

Flag leaf length, plant height, panicle length, and internode length were inhibited by the *sd1* gene (see table). However, the *sd1* gene increased the effective panicles per plant and harvest index. The yield of dwarf NILs was higher than that of tall NILs ($d = 2.54$). The *sd1* gene did not affect days to